

Follow-up questions to the user study

There are 16 questions in this survey.

Questions about the tested prototype

With these questions we would like to find out how you perceived the offer of explanation.

Have you made use of the explanation offer, i.e. had explanations displayed? *

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

Why didn't you display any explanations? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '1 [askedForExplanations]' (Have you made use of the explanation offer, i.e. had explanations displayed?)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

I had no questions for which I needed an explanation

I could not fit the questions I had into the categories offered

The offer of explanation was not present enough

Other

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the explanations offered by the tested software? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Agree	Rather agree	neutral	Rather disagree	Disagree	Not specified
The omnipresent offer of explanation (question mark in the bottom right corner of the software) was helpful	<input type="radio"/>					
It is helpful to always be able to find assistance in the same place	<input type="radio"/>					
The explanations were able to answer my questions	<input type="radio"/>					
I perceived the offer of explanation as disturbing	<input type="radio"/>					
was able to categorize my need for explanation into the three categories offered: algorithm, privacy, operation.	<input type="radio"/>					
I would like to see such an explainer in other software as well	<input type="radio"/>					

Which question remained unanswered?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Disagree' or 'Rather disagree' at question '3 [reactions]' (To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the explanations offered by the tested software? (The explanations were able to answer my questions))

Please write your answer here:

What bothered you about the explanation offer?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Agree' or 'Rather agree' at question '3 [reactions]' (To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the explanations offered by the tested software? (I perceived the offer of explanation as disturbing))

Please write your answer here:

Which question did not fit into the given categories? Do you have a suggestion for a suitable category?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Rather disagree' or 'Disagree' at question '3 [reactions]' (To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the explanations offered by the tested software? (was able to categorize my need for explanation into the three categories offered: algorithm, privacy, operation.))

Please write your answer here:

Further notes

Please write your answer here:

Explanation categories

In this second step, we would like to find out under which conditions users prefer to display explanations or do without them.

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your perception of the results of the tested software? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Agree	Rather agree	neutral	Rather disagree	Disagree	Not specified
The suggested topics for a contribution seemed appropriate to me	<input type="radio"/>					
The suggested articles for the linking task matched the text I highlighted	<input type="radio"/>					
An offer to explain the otherwise non-transparent suggestions helped me to understand the software better	<input type="radio"/>					
An offer to explain the otherwise non-transparent suggestions has strengthened my trust in the software (regardless of whether the offer was actually taken up)	<input type="radio"/>					
Getting content suggested is something I know from other software (videos I might like; people I might want to follow; ...).	<input type="radio"/>					

	Agree	Rather agree	neutral	Rather disagree	Disagree	Not specified
It is important to me to know how the software generates such suggestions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about privacy? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Agree	Rather agree	neutral	Rather disagree	Disagree	Not specified
Privacy in the digital environment is fundamentally important to me	<input type="radio"/>					
It is important for me to know why data about me is stored	<input type="radio"/>					
It is important for me to know where data about me is stored	<input type="radio"/>					
It is important for me to know how long data about me will be stored for	<input type="radio"/>					
The explanatory offer for these questions made it easier for me to disclose personal data such as my e-mail address in the tested software (regardless of whether the offer was actually taken up).	<input type="radio"/>					

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the operation of the tested software? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Agree	Rather agree	neutral	Rather disagree	Disagree	Not specified
Errors occurred during use (error message, red border, ...)	<input type="radio"/>					
If errors occurred: The explanatory offer helped me to understand and correct these errors	<input type="radio"/>					
It was unclear to me in at least one point why I could not press the "Next" button	<input type="radio"/>					
If there was any confusion: The offer of explanation helped me to find out how to move forward	<input type="radio"/>					
The operation of the software was intuitive for me	<input type="radio"/>					
Starting an action by selecting text is something I know from other software.	<input type="radio"/>					

At what point did errors occur or was it unclear why it did not continue? How did you solve the problem? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Agree' or 'Rather agree' at question '10 [usability]' (To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the operation of the tested software? (Errors occurred during use (error message, red border, ...)))

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Agree' or 'Rather agree' at question '10 [usability]' (To what extent do you agree with the following statements about the operation of the tested software? (It was unclear to me in at least one point why I could not press the "Next" button))

Please write your answer here:

Further notes

Please write your answer here:

Demographic Questions

How old are you? *

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

Which gender do you assign yourself to? *

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

male

female

diverse

Other

What is your profession at the moment? *

❗ Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

Training / Studies

Work

Other:

Rough details (social science studies, natural science studies, training in the trades) are sufficient, but you are also welcome to describe the field of activity in more detail (law studies, software engineer, ...).

To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your software use? *

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Agree	Rather agree	neutral	Rather disagree	Disagree
I work a lot with different software in a professional and / or private context.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel generally confident in the operation of software	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.